

careables.org

D6.3

**Validation and policy
recommendations including
Guidelines on Responsible
Research and Innovation
(RRI)**

Date
December 2020

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**Dissemination
Level**
Public

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Careables.org is managed by the Made4You project and has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 780298.

Document History

Version	Date	Contributor	Comments
0.1	23.10.2020	Elisabetta Biasin	Draft table of Contents
0.2	25.11.2020	Barbara Kieslinger	Input: section 4
0.3	10.12.2020	Elisabetta Biasin	First draft for internal review
0.4	11.12.2020	Erik Kamenjasevic	Internal review
0.5	11.12.2020	Anton Vedder (PI)	Internal review
0.6	14.12.2020	Elisabetta Biasin	Internal review feedback implementation
0.7	22.12.2020	Geraldine de Bastion (GIG)	External review
0.8	23.12.2020	Elisabetta Biasin Barbara Kieslinger	External review feedback implementation
1	23.12.2020	Elisabetta Biasin Barbara Kieslinger	Final version

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is the **third and final deliverable as part of the Made4You WP6 on 'Ethical and Legal Requirements'**. It represents the conclusive stage (T6.3 'Validation and Policy Recommendations') of the ethical and legal guidance provided in the Made4You project following the former tasks T6.1 ('In-depth legal analysis') and T6.2 ('Implementation of the legal and ethical requirements') led by KU Leuven. The present deliverable has **three aims**, corresponding to the following points.

- **Evaluation of the legal requirements identified and implemented in T6.1 and T6.2.** (section 2 'Evaluation of the legal requirements'). The section encompasses and provides the following grounding legal frameworks for Made4You:
 - 1) **Privacy and data protection law** (PDP), whose requirements concerned all phases of the Made4You project (including the setting of the Careables.org platform) and its stakeholders (makers, designers, engineers, healthcare professionals, individuals and their caregivers) (section 2.1)
 - 2) **Intellectual property rights** (IPRs), which may apply to the documentation of all careables projects (copyright) and may be relevant for their hardware parts (in the form of patent protection or other forms of IP protection for hardware) (section 2.2).
 - 3) **Liability and tort law** (LTL), whose paradigms are applicable for all the stakeholders involved in the co-design and co-creation of a careable (section 2.3).
 - 4) **Medical devices legislation** (MDL), which – in certain circumstances – may be relevant for specific categories of careables (section 2.4).

Finally, the same section 2 reports on **four additional recommendations** that were designed for makers during the execution of the Made4You project. They are addressed at those makers willing to co-design and co-create projects to face the diverse challenges brought by the **COVID-19** spread. These consist in the following: 1) do no harm, and be responsible; 2) evaluate applicability, risk and safety; 3) keep calm and choose a license; 4) check local laws, remember global reach (section 2.5).

- **Provision of policy recommendations to remove barriers and foster the flourishing of open healthcare solutions in the EU** (section 3). Policy recommendations, notably, call on to:
 - 1) Grant a **consumers' right to repair** and establish rules allowing reparability for independent repair providers;
 - 2) Consider **harmonising medical devices approval mechanisms in emergencies** (section 3.1).

Further to policy recommendations, the section suggests other topics that are worth to be investigated in more depth by future academic research. These concern the **role of makers** (and the uncertainty in considering them as professionals, hobbyists or differently); the novel opportunities for the **healthcare maker spaces in the EU**; the application of the **Good Samaritan doctrine/laws** in the maker's context (section 3.2).

- Providing guidelines on Responsible Research and Innovation (section 4). This section, based on the experience accrued in Made4You (section 4.1), proposes the **careables sustainable making principles** (section 4.3) – built on the Sustainable Making Principles for Makers (section 4.2) – which are:
 - 1) **Make things that make sense:** Create solutions that answer to real personal problems or needs.
 - 2) **Co-design with others:** Make space for diverse skills, competences, knowledge, and experiences to merge and come to new and meaningful solutions.
 - 3) **Empower people:** Teach others so that everyone can become more technologically literate and see the potentials.
 - 4) **Share How You Make:** Openly document the making of the project enabling its replication and choose the most appropriate licenses for your project.
 - 5) **Be aware of limits:** Consider any gaps of knowledge when you design for health and care, ask the people you design for and clinicians for support and feedback and follow quality and safety standards.

CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
CONTENTS	4
List of tables	5
List of figures	5
List of abbreviations	5
1. Introduction	6
1.1 Purpose of the document	6
1.2 Structure of the document	6
2. Evaluation of the legal requirements	8
2.1 Privacy and data protection	8
2.2 Intellectual property	9
2.3 Liability and tort law	11
2.4 Medical devices	12
2.5 Other considerations: Careables in the wake of the COVID19 outbreak	13
3. Policy recommendations to remove barriers and foster the flourishing of open healthcare solutions in the EU	14
3.1 Recommendations to policymakers	14
3.2 Open questions for future research	16
4. Guidelines on Responsible Research and Innovation	20
4.1 Introduction: RRI and the Made4You project	20
4.2 RRI and Critical Making	21
4.3 Responsible Making Principles	22
4.4 Additional RRI practice recommendations	23
5. Conclusions	26
6. References	27

List of tables

Table 1 COVID19 & Open-Source Hardware: Legal Recommendations for Makers	14
Table 2 Careables responsible making principles	23

List of figures

Figure 1 Careables responsible making principles	23
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List of abbreviations

CAD	Computer-aided Design
CC	Creative Commons
DIY	Do It Yourself
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EU	European Union
EUA	Emergency Use Authorisation
FDA	Food and Drug Administration Agency
IP	Intellectual Property
IPRs	Intellectual Property Rights
GA	Grant Agreement
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering
KUL	KU Leuven
FDA	Food and Drug Administration Agency
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IMDR	In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Device Regulation
TLT	Tort and Liability Law
MDL	Medical Device Law
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
MS	Member State
OSHW	Open Source Hardware
PDP	Privacy and Data Protection Law
RM	Responsible Making
R&I	Research and Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
WHO	World Health Organisation
WP	Work Package
ZSI	Centre for Social Innovation – ZSI

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The aim of Made4You WP6 'Legal and Ethical Aspects' is to guide the Consortium members on the relevant ethical and legal questions and produce a set of legal and ethical guidelines enabling maker communities to develop and share their knowledge in a transparent and legally sound way. This deliverable (D6.3) represents the continuation of Made4You D6.1 ('Legal and ethical inventory and in-depth analysis' (Kamenjašević & Biasin, 2018)) and D6.2 ('Implementation of the legal and ethical requirements' (Kamenjašević & Biasin, 2019)). D6.1 identified the relevant legal framework for the Made4You project and Careables.org, and D6.2 distilled the ethical and legal requirements in the form of understandable guidelines.

This document builds upon D6.1 and D6.2 and follows **three objectives**. The first objective is to **evaluate and validate** the implementation of requirements identified in D6.1 and D6.2. The second objective is to provide **recommendations to policymakers** regarding the co-design and co-creation of open healthcare solutions. The third objective is to **define guidelines for responsible research and innovation processes**.

1.2 Structure of the document

To fulfil the above-mentioned three-folded objectives, this deliverable is divided into three parts. A first part (**section 2**) contains the **evaluation of the legal requirements** provided in D6.1 and D6.2. Every sub-section is divided into three parts: **(1) evaluations**, where the identified legal requirements are briefly recalled having regard to D6.1 and D6.2; **(2) findings**: which briefly illustrates the implementation of these requirements; **(3) practical challenges ahead and recommendations**: which identifies some crucial aspects arose during the implementation phase. A conclusive sub-section (section 2.5) provides 'Other considerations: Careables.org in the wake of the COVID19 outbreak'.

A second part (**section 3**) contains '**Policy recommendations to remove barriers to the flourishing of open healthcare solutions in the EU**'. The section includes the 'Recommendations to policymakers' (section 3.1) which were identified in light of research activities carried out throughout the Made4You project. Further to this section, section 3.2 illustrates the 'Open questions for future research', which illustrates all the open issues that remain to be tackled by the legal research to nurture the policymaking debate at the EU and national level.

A third and final part (**section 4**) gives '**Guidelines on Responsible Research and Innovation**'. Section 4.1 ('Introduction: RRI and the Made4You project') briefly summarises the monitoring of RRI aspects carried out in the project. Section 4.2 ('RRI and Critical Making') explains the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). Section 4.3 contextualises RRI and Responsible Making (RM) in

the Made4You project, and section 4.4 concludes with 'Additional RRI practices and recommendations'.

2. Evaluation of the legal requirements

2.1 Privacy and data protection

EVALUATION As illustrated in D6.1,¹ the privacy and data protection legal framework is relevant to the Made4You project,² for Careables.org and the categories of stakeholders that use the platform to co-design and co-create the *careables*.³ The said framework becomes relevant since the Careables.org platform implies the processing of personal data of individuals or their caregivers; and because Made4You entailed the involvement of individuals in certain project's activities.⁴ The data concerning these subjects are personal data, and often they concern their health.⁵ As such, they pertain to particular categories of personal data foreseen by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which requires particular safeguards to be respected.⁶ D6.1 identified the legal framework and aspects relevant to the execution of the Made4You project, including the setting up of the Careables.org platform. D6.2 integrated the description of the legal framework with legal guidelines for the Made4You project, the Careables.org platform and the *careables*.

FINDINGS The protection of personal data had to be respected throughout all phases of the **Made4You project**.⁷ Mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data had to be ensured in workshops and meetups.⁸ Data protection rules were also essential for the **Careables.org platform**.⁹ The partners were guided on the data protection by design and by design¹⁰ and security data protection requirements.¹¹ Furthermore, during the creation of the platform, the partners evaluated the roles and the relevant processing activities of the Careables.org platform. These were detailed in the platform's privacy policy, to inform the data subjects of the processing.¹² Finally, privacy and data protection requirements are relevant to the category of **makers, designers, engineers**.¹³ During the design of a *careable*, they shall respect the data protection by design

¹ For the full analysis of the data protection legal framework in Made4You, see D6.1, section 2.

² See D6.1 section 2.5 ('Key data protection legal requirements and recommendations for Made4You').

³ See D6.1, section 2.6 ('Key data protection legal requirements and recommendations for Careables platform').

⁴ See details on Made4You project activities in D6.1, at pp. 30-32.

⁵ See D6.1, section 2.3.3.2. ('Special categories of personal data') for a broader overview.

⁶ See D6.1, section 2.4 ('Key principles and rules of data protection law').

⁷ See D6.1, section 2.6.2 ('Data protection by design').

⁸ See also Kieslinger, Barbara, Schäfer, T., Fabian, C. M., Kamenjašević, E., & Verhenneman, G. (2018). Made4You D8.2. POPD - Requirement No. 2.

⁹ See D6.1, section 2.6.2 ('Data protection by design').

¹⁰ See D6.2, section 3.2 ('PDP guidelines').

¹¹ See D6.2, section 2.4.3 (Security of processing').

¹² Privacy policy is available at <https://www.welder.app/privacy-policy>.

¹³ See Biasin, E. & Kamenjašević, E. (2020). Made4You D5.3 Careables White Paper on Legal Guidelines Common legal challenges in OSH for healthcare. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/record/4086144#.X8-fpdhKg2w>.

and by default as well as the data quality principles.¹⁴ Makers, designers and engineers were recommended to demonstrate compliance with them in all phases of the design, development and use of a project, i.e. from an abstract idea to prototyping, to the creation of the healthcare project, to the upload of the project on Careables.org.¹⁵ When designing a project, makers, designers and engineers shall be aware that information provided by the individual and the caregiver may be sensitive data.¹⁶ If they develop technologies that have particular features allowing to infer certain health parameters (e.g. monitoring heart or insulin rates), they shall be cautious as these often are personal data concerning health.¹⁷ Finally, any CAD file or design uploaded on the platform shall make the least use possible of information concerning individuals, in compliance with the principle of data minimisation.¹⁸

PRACTICAL CHALLENGES AHEAD FOR CAREABLES.ORG AND RECOMMENDATIONS The roles and responsibilities under a data protection point of view were evaluated as part of the activities related to the Made4You project. However, with the termination of the Made4You project, there may be new scenarios in the ownership and management of the Careables.org platform. Therefore, **after the end of the Made4You** project, the owners of Careables.org and the entities in charge of establishing the purposes and means of the processing activities, shall assess and eventually **reconsider the allocation of roles and responsibilities under a data protection point of view**. This activity shall be in line with the most recent EU acquis and guidance on data protection.¹⁹ The change in role and responsibilities, if any, may require changing information policies, as well as contractual settings amongst the involved entities.

2.2 Intellectual property

EVALUATION: The principal aim of Careables.org is to foster knowledge sharing online and to allow the users of the platforms to share and reproduce their projects without fewer constraints possible. Therefore, the analysis of intellectual property aspects in Made4You was important.²⁰ D6.1 outlined the intellectual property legal landscape for uploading the OSHW projects on the

¹⁴ *ibid.*, at p. 13

¹⁵ *ibid.*

¹⁶ For considerations on the nature of citizen science, data protection and household exemptions that might apply, see Dove, E. S., & Chen, J. (2020). To What Extent Does the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Apply to Citizen Scientist-Led Health Research with Mobile Devices? *The Journal of Law, Medicine & Ethics*, 48(1_suppl), 187–195. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1073110520917046>.

¹⁷ See Biasin, E. & Kamenjašević, E. (2020). Made4You D5.3 Careables White Paper on Legal Guidelines Common legal challenges in OSH for healthcare. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/record/4086144#.X8-fpdhKg2w>.

¹⁸ *ibid.*

¹⁹ See e.g. EDPB. (2020). Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR.

https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/edpb/files/consultation/edpb_guidelines_202007_controllerprocessor_en.pdf.

²⁰ See D6.1, at p. 6.

D6.3 Validation and policy recommendations including Guidelines on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

platform²¹. D6.2 provided IPRs guidelines about intellectual property rights and licensing, for the Made4You Consortium partners and for the Careables.org users when developing or reproducing a *careable*.²²

FINDINGS The essential features of intellectual property law for *careables* primarily concern copyright and patent law. First, **copyright applies to the documentation** of *careables* projects.²³ The EU copyright system grants exclusive rights to the author of a copyrighted work as soon as such work is created.²⁴ When users upload project documentation (including models, designs, software but also photos, CAD files, manuals or instructions) on Careables.org, they must ensure they are not uploading any material that is already protected by copyright (to avoid the risk of infringing any others' intellectual property right).²⁵ Once this aspect is verified, users shall choose the license they deem appropriate for their works as the selection of the proper license is essential to enable further use and reproduction of *careable* documentation.²⁶ While there exist different versions or variations of Open Source Hardware licenses, the recommended approach in Careables.org is to adopt the Creative Commons (CC) licenses.²⁷ Second, **tangible products (i.e. hardware), generally do not enjoy copyright protection**.²⁸ Therefore, copyright applies to the *careables* documentation but not the reproduction thereof into tangible objects. Patent protection applies upon fulfilling specific requirements²⁹ to tangible objects. In this case, users remain with two options: a person obtains patent protection for innovative parts of hardware and decides to apply an open source license to it. Alternatively, a person decides not to request patent protection, and anyone may reproduce the *careable* into tangible objects as documented in the platform, as long as copyright rules concerning the project's documentation are respected.³⁰

PRACTICAL CHALLENGES FOR MAKERS AND RECOMMENDATIONS: The most recurrent practical challenges for makers for respecting intellectual property rights is inherently linked to the nature of maker spaces or Fablabs. Often, the process of co-design and co-creation of the project follows a culture of informal sharing.³¹ It is, therefore, of utmost importance to enhance awareness on intellectual property rights and licensing knowledge. To foster awareness and respect of IPRs, we concur with DiDIY (2017, p. 12) in the proposed

²¹ See D6.1, section 3 ('IPRs framework').

²² See D6.2, section 4 ('Careables & IPRs').

²³ See D6.1, section 3.2 ('Copyright').

²⁴ *ibid.*

²⁵ See D6.2, section 4.2 ('IPR guidelines').

²⁶ *ibid.*

²⁷ See D6.1, section 3.4 ('Creative Commons licenses').

²⁸ See D6.1, section 3.5 ('Patent rights').

²⁹ See D6.1, p. 57.

³⁰ For problematics in this respect, see Biasin, E. & Kamenjašević, E. (2019). Careables – end user innovation for open diy healthcare solutions. <https://sites.google.com/view/oui2019/program-oui-2019-at-utrecht-university/book-of-abstracts-oui-2019>.

³¹ See also DiDIY D7.4 DIDY-Related policy recommendations, at p. 12.

recommendation for maker spaces or Fablabs to adopt licensing policy options or recommend makers specific licenses for certain types of works.³²

2.3 Liability and tort law

EVALUATION: Main aspects of liability and tort law were outlined in D6.1³³ and D6.2³⁴. The legal analysis in Made4You privileged the principles of the common law model (for its language accessibility, on the one hand, and its affinity to the French model which inspired the other Member States, on the other hand), and built upon existing legal literature available.

FINDINGS There is a **variety of stakeholders that collaborate for the co-creation of a careable**: designers, makers, and engineers; healthcare professionals; individuals and their caregivers. In some instances, these stakeholders may use 3D-printers to reproduce the CAD files. Every of the mentioned stakeholder in the co-design and co-creation of the product has a role and thus may be responsible, according to **tort law principles**. This happens if the *careable* is defective or if damage occurs to a person or an object, and the stakeholder did not act with due diligence.³⁵ In addition to the duty of care / due diligence standard³⁶, **strict liability** paradigms may apply, if the product is industrially produced (i.e. if the manufacturer thereof produced it in the course of a business).³⁷ However, the application of strict liability depends on the specific case at hand.³⁸ Finally, it is worth to note there is **no common framework in Europe concerning civil law**.³⁹ Every EU Member State has its own framework, depending on the doctrines and ultimately, the history of law and the reforms that succeeded at the national level. Ultimately, rules foreseen by international private law and others have a crucial role in determining the applicable legislation.

PRACTICAL CHALLENGES FOR MAKERS AND RECOMMENDATIONS: A practical remark for TLT resides in the observed makers', designers' and engineers' tendency in **exempting themselves from any liability aspect** that may occur from the use of the *careable*. **Liability exemption, warranties and warning clauses, disclaimers, and insurance practices** are recommended approaches in this regard.⁴⁰ However, terms and conditions exempting from liability are prohibited or limited in certain states.⁴¹ Further comparative research should help to

³² *ibid.*

³³ See D6.1, section 4 ('Made4You, Careables, and implications concerning Liability').

³⁴ See D6.2, section 5 ('Careables & liability').

³⁵ It is essential to note that, the establishment of the degree of responsibility of a maker under civil law ultimately depends on the consideration of his/her role and activity (see *infra* section 3.2).

³⁶ See D6.1, p. 60.

³⁷ See D6.2, p. 22.

³⁸ *ibid.*

³⁹ See D6.1, p. 61.

⁴⁰ See D6.2, p. 23.

⁴¹ E.g., see Italian civil code, art. 1229 'Any agreement excluding or limiting the liability of a party for willful misconduct or gross negligence is invalid. Any preventive agreement of exemption or limitation of liability is also invalid for cases in which the fact of a party and her auxiliaries constitutes a violation of obligations deriving from rules of public order'.

elucidate applications and differences in national laws so to provide makers with a sound tool within which they could act safely.

2.4 Medical devices

EVALUATION: Given the nature of *careables* intrinsically linked to their application in the healthcare domain, one may wonder whether some of these may be considered as medical devices, as defined by the applicable laws. The **EU medical devices legal framework was approached** in the Made4You project in D6.1⁴² and D6.2⁴³. D6.1 presented the relevant legal frameworks in the EU on medical devices, i.e. the currently applicable directives on medical devices⁴⁴ which are in the process of being replaced by the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR) and the *in vitro* Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation (IMDR). D6.2 guided the new scope of the MDR (which will now be extended to devices having the purposes of *prediction and prognosis* of a disease) and gave **guidelines for makers to evaluate the scope and applicability of MDL**.⁴⁵ These guidelines were **integrated with practical examples** to facilitate the understanding for professional makers, designers or manufacturing entities of what could qualify as a medical device.⁴⁶

FINDINGS: Further to the guidelines and the practical examples provided in D6.2, the deliverables concluded that some kinds of *careables* might qualify as medical devices.⁴⁷ This evaluation must be done by makers, designers, engineers or any other person or legal entity that identify him/herself as a medical device manufacturer. As a consequence, **not all careables qualify as medical devices**.⁴⁸ **Some may qualify** as such, **only if** the maker, designer, engineer or the manufacturer establishes that the device pursues one of **the medical purposes** defined by MDL, and reports it in the product documentation when putting the device on the market.⁴⁹

PRACTICAL CHALLENGES FOR MAKERS AND RECOMMENDATIONS: Navigating the law concerning medical devices may not be an easy task for makers. Practical challenges start from the beginning, when makers should evaluate whether the product being reproduced is a medical device, or whether they should consider themselves as a medical device manufacturer, according to MDL.⁵⁰ The evaluation

⁴² See D6.1, section 4.3 ('DIY environments and medical devices').

⁴³ See D6.2, section 6 ('Careables and medical devices').

⁴⁴ Council Directive 93/42/EEC of 14 June 1993 concerning medical devices (Medical Devices Directive (MDD)); Council Directive 90/385/EEC on Active Implantable Medical Devices (AIMDD); Directive 98/79/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on *in vitro* Diagnostic Medical Devices (IVDMD). See D6.1, section 4.3.2.

⁴⁵ See D6.2, section 6.3, at p. 28.

⁴⁶ D6.2, section 6.3.1.

⁴⁷ *ibid.*

⁴⁸ *ibid.*

⁴⁹ See MDD, art 1(2); MDR art 2(1).

⁵⁰ See also, Biasin, E. & Kamenjašević, E. (2020). D5.3 Careables White Paper on Legal Guidelines Common legal challenges in OSH for healthcare. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/record/4086144#.X8-fpdhKg2w>

of these aspects (scope and applicability)⁵¹ is crucial, as it determines whether it is mandatory to comply with MDL requirements.⁵²

2.5 Other considerations: Careables in the wake of the COVID19 outbreak

The advent of the **COVID19** put under pressure the provision in healthcare organisations of certain medical supplies and products⁵³. Throughout 2020, networks of makers joined their forces at the global scale.⁵⁴ They set up initiatives to share knowledge and find solutions to face product shortages or everyday challenges caused by the pandemic.⁵⁵ Any swift response to an immediate healthcare need, nevertheless, requires the evaluation and respect of safety requirements established by the laws. For this reason, in its April 2020 guidelines, KU Leuven proposed **four understandable recommendations to guide makers in their COVID19 response actions**.⁵⁶ These are summarised in the table below.

	<p>Do no harm, and be responsible</p>	<p><i>Just like everyone else, makers have a duty to refrain from causing harm. Makers and designers</i></p>
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⁵¹ For further guidance see Biasin, E., & Kamenjašević, E. (2020). Open Source Hardware and Healthcare Collaborative Platforms: Common Legal Challenges. *Journal of Open Hardware*, 4(1), 7. <https://doi.org/10.5334/joh.31>

⁵² Further steps may imply: device classification, declaration of conformity, manufacturer's and device's registration as established by MDL. For a comprehensive overview of a device's regulatory path in the context of patient innovation, 'from the idea to the market' see Maffei, S., Bianchini, M., Parini, B., & Cipriani, L. (2019). *MakeToCare2. La patient innovation in Italia tra progetto e mercato*. Libraccio Editore. https://www.maketocare.it/-/media/EMS/Conditions/RareDiseases/Brands/Maketocare-IT/ReportMTC2_2019.pdf?h= at p. 64.

⁵³ See e.g. WHO. (2020). Shortage of personal protective equipment endangering health workers worldwide. <https://www.who.int/news/item/03-03-2020-shortage-of-personal-protective-equipment-endangering-health-workers-worldwide>.

⁵⁴ For an brief overview and references to makers initiatives related to COVID19, see Biasin, E. (2020) *Stampa 3D in sanità: sfide e opportunità ai tempi del covid-19*. <https://www.agendadigitale.eu/sanita/stampa-3d-in-sanita-sfide-e-opportunita-ai-tempi-del-covid-19/>.

⁵⁵ See Biasin, Elisabetta, & Kamenjasevic, Erik. (2020). COVID19 & Open-Source Hardware: Legal Recommendations for Makers. *CiTiP Blog*. <https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/blog/covid19-open-source-hardware-legal-recommendations-for-makers/>.

⁵⁶ These recommendations were designed and illustrated in the context of online talks and webinars concerning maker's response to COVID19 challenges. See Biasin, E. (2020). *Open Source Hardware in Healthcare. A focus on medical devices and their qualification*. https://limo.libis.be/primo-explore/fulldisplay?docid=LIRIAS3064065&context=L&vid=Lirias&search_scope=Lirias&tab=default_tab&lang=en_US;

Biasin, Elisabetta, & Kamenjašević, Erik. (2020). *COVID19 & Open Source Hardware. Legal recommendations for Makers*. https://limo.libis.be/primo-explore/fulldisplay?docid=LIRIAS3072831&context=L&vid=Lirias&search_scope=Lirias&tab=default_tab&lang=en_US, talks respectively available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Yy9LcnUHz8A>, and <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rwwIHQ0--tQ>.

	Evaluate applicability, safety & risks	<p><i>should act responsibly. If something goes wrong, there is room to be held liable</i></p>
	Keep calm and choose a license	<p><i>Some of the projects to be reproduced (for example face masks, filters, face shields) might be covered by medical devices or personal protective equipment laws. Makers should check carefully if it is the case. If so, safety requirements must be followed.</i></p> <p><i>Makers should ensure that there will be no intellectual property rights infringements (example: copyright, patent).</i></p>
	Check local laws, remember global reach	<p><i>Extraordinary circumstances may imply new exceptional rules. Makers should check new guidance or waivers. Collaborative platforms have a global reach: makers should evaluate the applicability of other local laws when co-creating or replicating projects.</i></p>

Table 1 COVID19 & Open-Source Hardware: Legal Recommendations for Makers

3. Policy recommendations to remove barriers and foster the flourishing of open healthcare solutions in the EU

3.1 Recommendations to policymakers

1. GRANT CONSUMERS' RIGHT TO REPAIR AND ESTABLISH RULES ALLOWING REPAIRABILITY FOR INDEPENDENT REPAIR PROVIDERS

Makers and Fablabs have not only a crucial role in the design and co-creation tangible objects. They may play an essential role in their repair, too (e.g. makers they may repair a product individually; or, Fablabs may provide tools or even

services for repair).⁵⁷ In this perspective, the right to repair debate becomes relevant for Careables.org and the *careables*.⁵⁸ In Europe, the argument has been growing in its significance, also thanks to the new policies on **circular economy** adopted at the EU level.⁵⁹ A 'consumers' right to repair', however, does not exist yet under the current EU legal framework.⁶⁰ In this perspective, several associations of consumers are joining their forces to ask for its enshrinement under the EU law.⁶¹ There are promising signals that indicate its forthcoming establishment (having regard, for instance, the EU Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan,⁶² and the recent European Parliament Motion for Resolution)⁶³. In order to support and provide input in the legislator's evaluative process concerning the right to repair, we provide the following recommendations.

- First, to ensure repairability, accessibility to 'repair manuals' is essential. EU rules should aim at establishing accessibility requirements for **repair information and spare parts**. New EU norms should ensure access to repair and maintenance information to independent repairers and do-it-yourself (DIY) repair (thus including Fablabs/maker spaces).
- Second, and consequent, EU rules **should foresee design requirements, ensuring ease of disassembly, replacement & upgradeability of key components of products**.⁶⁴

⁵⁷ The repair may concern all kind of products, including medical devices. However, for the sake of simplicity in this paragraph we refer to products not qualifying as such – as the evaluation on medical devices right to repair would require additional evaluations and research that would exceed the scope and purposes of the present deliverable. Aspects underlying the right to repair for medical devices, however, are under-researched and deserve more attention in legal literature. For general considerations on medical devices and right to repair, see—amongst his many articles—Koebler, J. (2020). Hospitals need to repair ventilators. Manufacturers are making that impossible. <https://www.vice.com/en/article/wxekgx/hospitals-need-to-repair-ventilators-manufacturers-are-making-that-impossible>.

⁵⁸ On the consumer's aspect related to the right to repair in the EU, Svensson, S., Richter, J. L., Maitre-Ekern, E., Pihlajarinne, T., Maignet, A., & Dalhammar, C. (2018). The Emerging 'Right to Repair' legislation in the EU and the U.S.. Paper presented at Going Green CARE INNOVATION 2018, Vienna, Austria.

⁵⁹ European Commission. (2019) Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. The European Green Deal. See also European Commission. (2020). Circular Economy Action Plan. For a cleaner and more competitive Europe.

⁶⁰ On this conclusion, see Terryn, E. (2019). A Right to Repair? Towards Sustainable Remedies in Consumer Law. *European Review of Private Law*, 4, 851–874.

⁶¹ See e.g. Repair Europe and the organisations under its umbrella: <https://repair.eu/>; <https://repair.eu/our-members/>.

⁶² European Commission, 2020 (n. **Error! Bookmark not defined.**), see particularly, at p. 8: 'In addition, the Commission will work towards establishing a new 'right to repair' and consider new horizontal material rights for consumers for instance as regards availability of spare parts or access to repair (...)'

⁶³ European Parliament. (2020). Parliament wants to grant EU consumers a "right to repair" <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20201120IPR92118/parliament-wants-to-grant-eu-consumers-a-right-to-repair>

⁶⁴ For an in-depth analysis on product design requirements, see Keirsblick, B., Terryn, E., Michel, A. & Alogna, I., (2020). Sustainable consumption and consumer protection legislation. In-Depth D6.3 Validation and policy recommendations including Guidelines on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

2. CONSIDER HARMONISING MEDICAL DEVICES APPROVAL MECHANISMS FOR EMERGENCY SITUATIONS

The spread of COVID19 put healthcare organisations worldwide under pressure. In some instances⁶⁵, certain hospitals have suffered from the lack of sufficient medical equipment or certain component of medical devices. In these cases, emergency production (even done by makers, designers, engineers) have proven essential to ensure the continuity of healthcare services provisions.⁶⁶ However, due to regulatory complexity, some barriers for makers, designers, engineers in producing emergency equipment, seem to be in place in the EU (Pearce, 2020). In the US, the **Food and Drug Administration Agency** (FDA) published its guidance for **Emergency Use Authorisation** (EUA) in 2017.⁶⁷ The same Agency, in 2020, issued 'emergency use authorisations' for specific technologies.⁶⁸ In the EU, regulatory authorities provided guidance to contrast certain challenges posed by the pandemic.⁶⁹ However, it seems that there are no provisions in the EU corresponding to the US EUA.⁷⁰ Some rules on 'compassionate use' (i.e. simplified regulatory pathways, for drugs or medical devices approvals for patients with life-threatening conditions (Tsuyuki et al., 2016)) do exist. However, they concern medicinal products only and not medical devices.⁷¹ The issue seems to be left at the national level. Only some Member States have national laws referring to **compassionate use** for medical devices.⁷² Thus, the situation, at the moment, appears fragmented. For this reason, **EU level guidance, to set unified procedures to approve medical devices during emergencies would be beneficial in enhancing the level of harmonisation of EU for medical devices regulations.**

3.2 Open questions for future research

1. THE ROLE OF MAKERS: BETWEEN HOBBYISTS AND PROFESSIONALS?

Analysis for the Committee on Internal Market and Consumer Protection (IMCO), Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies, European Parliament, Luxembourg.

⁶⁵ See e.g. FDA. (2020). Medical Device Shortages During the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/coronavirus-covid-19-and-medical-devices/medical-device-shortages-during-covid-19-public-health-emergency>.

⁶⁶ See section below, point n. 3.

⁶⁷ FDA. (2017). Emergency Use Authorization of Medical Products and Related Authorities. <https://www.fda.gov/media/97321/download>.

⁶⁸ See FDA. (2020) Emergency Use Authorization. <https://www.fda.gov/emergency-preparedness-and-response/mcm-legal-regulatory-and-policy-framework/emergency-use-authorization>

⁶⁹ See European Commission. (2020). Public health https://ec.europa.eu/info/live-work-travel-eu/coronavirus-response/public-health_en#ensuring-the-availability-of-supplies-and-equipment.

⁷⁰ See Perez, S. (2020). Expanded Access Programs for Medical Devices. <https://www.raps.org/news-and-articles/news-articles/2018/4/expanded-access-programs-for-medical-devices>.

⁷¹ EMA. (n.d.) Compassionate use. <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory/research-development/compassionate-use>

⁷² See Italy, for instance: Decreto Legislativo 24 febbraio 1997, n.46, Article 11(14-bis).

The analysis of Made4You legal aspects led to the following question: how makers are or should be considered by the law?⁷³ As already explained in D6.1 and D6.2, **the role of makers** may challenge the traditional categories established by the legal frameworks, especially on product liability.⁷⁴ It is difficult to establish whether a maker may be considered as doing a professional activity or, on the contrary, carrying out a household activity.⁷⁵ As already observed, to establish if a maker is a professional or a hobbyist, a case-by-case analysis is necessary.⁷⁶ Furthermore, the distinction between professional/household unlocks different paradigms of liability for the makers. Should the maker be considered as performing a professional activity, product laws – and the higher standards of strict liability⁷⁷ – shall apply. In the opposite case, in which the maker is considered in a household scope, lower standards of due diligence⁷⁸ stemming from tort law will apply. The dichotomy 'household/professional' characterising the role of makers induced scholars in interrogating themselves on the traditional figures of law.⁷⁹ Starting some years ago, scholars hypothesised notions such as prosumers⁸⁰ some other even theorised hypothesizing in law a *tertium genus* category, i.e. micro-sellers (Berkowitz, 2015). Nevertheless, as Lemley maintains –and Daly develops further⁸¹ – Berkowitz's theorisation fails to address the law enforceability problem for product liability laws. Far from being settled in the academic environment, this aspect seems to remain an open issue that will need to be addressed further by researchers and policymakers.

2. HEALTHCARE MAKER SPACES. A NEW WAY FORWARD IN THE EU?

In the last 15-20 years, we assisted at the flourishing of the maker movement around the world.⁸² In most recent years, makers' interests towards healthcare solutions grew, as also testified by their growing presence on healthcare collaborative platforms.⁸³ Within the same trend, maker spaces have entered healthcare settings, such as hospitals and other health and care facilities.⁸⁴ In the

⁷³ The question is not new. See e.g. Daly, A. (2016). Socio-Legal Aspects of the 3D Printing Revolution. Palgrave Macmillan UK. <https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-51556-8>.

⁷⁴ See D6.1, at p. 67.

⁷⁵ As already observed, to establish if a maker is a professional or a hobbyist, a case-by-case analysis is necessary following the EU guidelines or at the national level (if any).

⁷⁶ See D6.2, at p. 23

⁷⁷ For considerations on the notions of strict liability and due diligence see D6.1, at pp. 60-62.

⁷⁸ Idem. See also (Biasin & Kamenjašević, 2020).

⁷⁹ See Caeran, M. (2016). La digitalizzazione del prodotto difettoso: Stampa 3D e responsabilità civile. The Trento Law and Technology Research Group Student Paper n. 24. 276.

⁸⁰ See outline provided by Daly (n. **Error! Bookmark not defined.**), at p. 66.

⁸¹ See Daly, at p. 69.

⁸² See Davies, S. (2017). Hackerspaces: Making the maker movement. Cambridge, UK Malden, MA, USA: Polity.

⁸³ On healthcare collaborative platforms, see Biasin, Elisabetta, & Kamenjasevic, Erik. (2020). Open Source Hardware and Healthcare Collaborative Platforms: Common Legal Challenges. Journal of Open Hardware, 4(1), 1-8. For a comparative overview of healthcare collaborative platforms, see also Zahid, A. et al. (2019). The development of innovation sharing platforms for low cost and do-it-yourself assistive technology in low & middle-income countries. In WHO Global Report on Assistive Technology. Geneva, Switzerland, 22–23 August 2019, pp. 359–376.

⁸⁴ The Medical Futurist. (2018) A Revolution in Access to Healthcare: DIY Labs and Makerspaces. <https://medicalfuturist.com/revolution-access-healthcare-diy-labs-makerspaces/>.

US, the phenomenon became a reality through, for example, the MakerNurse project⁸⁵ and the establishment of the MakerHealth⁸⁶ initiative.⁸⁷ In the EU, examples of maker spaces and clinician innovation are present in some MS.⁸⁸ Interestingly in this regard, the **new EU regulation on medical devices contains provisions that may pave the way and favour health institutions⁸⁹ in setting up healthcare maker spaces.** According to the MDR,⁹⁰ 'health institutions should have the possibility of manufacturing, modifying and using devices in-house' in order to address 'on a non-industrial scale, the specific needs of target patient groups which cannot be met at the appropriate level of performance by an equivalent device available on the market'.⁹¹ The same institutions would also benefit from less stringent rules in the manufacturing of medical devices.⁹² However, little studies have focused their analysis on the impact of maker space and clinician innovation in hospitals in the improvement of social welfare.⁹³ The setting up these environments could be promoted in many ways - including highlighting the economic benefits this eventuality might entail. For instance, Svensson & Hartmann in their study (2018) found that setting up and operating maker spaces at least in hospital contexts, imply a high rate of return investments. Comparative⁹⁴ research should investigate further on the effects of user innovation initiatives in healthcare, as they could support national or European policies in the healthcare maker space promotion.

3. MAKER'S RESPONSIBILITY AND GOOD SAMARITAN LAWS

In 2020, there have been some cases in which makers, designers and engineers created, modified and reproduced devices to cope with the healthcare emergency caused by COVID19.⁹⁵ To give an example, in May 2020, to remedy the shortage of medical supply, a team of designers and engineers, in partnership with a 3D-printing company (Isinnova) converted snorkelling masks into emergency masks

⁸⁵ See <http://makernurse.com/>. See Schiller, B. (2016). MakerNurse Is Tapping Grassroots Innovation To Improve Patient Care. <https://www.fastcompany.com/3057767/makernurse-is-tapping-grassroots-innovation-to-improve-patient-care>.

⁸⁶ See <https://makerhealth.co/>, and <https://www.utmb.edu/maker>.

⁸⁷ See Geere, D. (2016). This startup is helping nurses prototype and innovate. <https://www.wired.co.uk/article/anna-young-makerhealth-makernurse>.

⁸⁸ See Svensson, P. O., & Hartmann, R. K. (2018). Policies to promote user innovation_ Makerspaces and clinician innovation in Swedish hospitals. *Research Policy*, 12.

⁸⁹ According to the MDR, healthcare institutions means 'an organisation the primary purpose of which is the care or treatment of patients or the promotion of public health' (MDR, Article 2(36)).

⁹⁰ See MDR, Recital 30.

⁹¹ *ibid.*

⁹² See MDR, Recital 30, second sentence and Article 5(5).

⁹³ See Svensson & Hartmann (n **Error! Bookmark not defined.**).

⁹⁴ Svensson & Hartmann's study was limited to the Finland case.

⁹⁵ See 'COVID19 Covid-19 response from global makers: the Careables cases of global design and local production' (Kieslinger et al., forthcoming and on file with the authors) for a wider perspective of makers' response facing COVID19 challenges. On the COVID19 emergency, maker's responses and the use of 3D-printing, see Biasin, E. (2020). *Stampa 3D in sanità: Sfide e opportunità ai tempi del covid-19. Agenda Digitale*. <https://www.agendadigitale.eu/sanita/stampa-3d-in-sanita-sfide-e-opportunita-ai-tempi-del-covid-19/>.

for hospital respirators.⁹⁶ Decathlon (the manufacturing company of the snorkelling masks), shared the CAD design file of the mask so the team of designers and engineers could design a new connection piece ('Charlotte valve') to the hospital respirator, which was 3D-printed.⁹⁷ Analogous examples followed in Italy⁹⁸ and elsewhere in Europe.⁹⁹ ¹⁰⁰ The rise of these cases and similar cases in the EU and around the world have led academics questioning about the degree of liability makers, designers, engineers, should have when intervening in emergencies. Some scholars (Vu-Dinh & Marlan, 2020, p. 1) have argued that certain exceptions to patent and copyright liability should exist during the pandemic, especially for those who are volunteers contributing to response efforts. This is worth to be further explored in research, not only for the US but also for the EU context.¹⁰¹ Furthermore, liability aspects imply a second and broader consideration. In emergencies, makers, designers, and engineers may decide to act and produce medical items to create equipment that due to product shortage would be unavailable for patients. Such a response, moved by ethical judgements (e.g. fabricating a respiratory valve to avoid suffering or other deadly complications for patients) of makers/designers/engineers, may nevertheless be

⁹⁶ See Vincent, M. (2020) Italian medics are converting Decathlon snorkeling masks into 'homemade' ventilators to cope with coronavirus crisis. <https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-8165461/Italian-medics-convert-snorkelling-masks-homemade-ventilators-coronavirus-crisis.html>; See also, Isinnova. (2020). Easy COVID19. <https://www.isinnova.it/easy-covid19/>.

⁹⁷ Sparaciarì, A. (2020) Così la maschera da sub di Decathlon si trasforma in un respiratore. La nuova trovata della Isinnova. <https://it.businessinsider.com/isinnova-maschere-snorkeling-terapia-intensiva/>.

⁹⁸ See Dalla Mura, M. T. & Costa, C. (2020). Stampa 3D e Sanità: innovazione e creatività ai tempi del Coronavirus. <https://www.internet4things.it/smart-health/stampa-3d-e-sanita-innovazione-e-creativita-ai-tempi-del-coronavirus/>.

⁹⁹ See Reuters. (2020) European researchers retrofit snorkel masks for coronavirus fight. <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-health-coronavirus-czech-snorkel-mask-idUSKBN21H2Z5>.

¹⁰⁰ In this case, Decathlon voluntarily provided the CAD file to the team to face the emergency. However, in some instances, the design of certain medical equipment is covered by intellectual property rights, such as a patent. Thus, the manufacturing entity may be less eager to share its knowledge and risks of being sued by original manufacturers may arise. The team of designers and engineers reproduced and 3D-printed valves for respiratory masks, which were protected by patents. This eventuality was initially paved in another case in Italy, see Moody, G. (2020). Volunteers 3D-Print Unobtainable \$11,000 Valve For \$1 To Keep Covid-19 Patients Alive; Original Manufacturer Threatens To Sue <https://www.techdirt.com/articles/20200317/04381644114/volunteers-3d-print-unobtainable-11000-valve-1-to-keep-covid-19-patients-alive-original-manufacturer-threatens-to-sue.shtml>. Sparaciarì, A. (2020). Coronavirus, a Brescia manca una valvola per i rianimatori: ingegneri e fisici la stampano in 3D in sei ore. <https://it.businessinsider.com/coronavirus-manca-la-valvola-per-uno-strumento-di-rianimazione-e-noi-la-stampiamo-in-3d-accade-nellospedale-di-chiari-brescia/>; Peters, V. (2020). Volunteers produce 3D-printed valves for life-saving coronavirus treatments <https://www.theverge.com/2020/3/17/21184308/coronavirus-italy-medical-3d-print-valves-treatments>.

¹⁰¹ For further remarks on IPRs and COVID19 response, see also Mahr, D., & Dickel, S. (2020). Rethinking intellectual property rights and commons-based peer production in times of crisis: The case of COVID-19 and 3D printed medical devices. *Journal of Intellectual Property Law & Practice*, 15(9), 7.

in contrast or non-fully compliant with legal provisions concerning product safety requirements. In this regard, by building on the 'Good Samaritan' doctrine¹⁰², some scholars have maintained that there is a need to limit liability on the part of the designers, makers, and users (e.g., medical professionals) of Open Source medical Hardware (Pearce, 2020). The same (Pearce, 2020) recommended the 'development of good-Samaritan laws to protect makers and designers of open medical hardware, as well as to compel those with the knowledge that will save lives to share it'. To support the development of analogous policies in the EU, academic legal research should compare differences in the EU legal systems and propose relevant solutions.¹⁰³ We concur with Pearce (2020, p. 12) in affirming that **substantial further research is needed concerning the issue of Good Samaritan laws and healthcare open hardware such as the *careables*.**

4. Guidelines on Responsible Research and Innovation

4.1 Introduction: RRI and the Made4You project

The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach is promoted throughout the Horizon 2020 objectives.¹⁰⁴ It consists in adopting an inclusive approach to research and innovation (R&I), to allow all societal actors to work together during the whole research and innovation process.¹⁰⁵ In practice, RRI entails the assessment of potential implications and societal expectations with regard to R&I. According to the European Commission¹⁰⁶, and as anticipated in the project Grant Agreement (GA), key elements of an R&I policy include the monitoring of the following aspects: public engagement in R&I activities; open access to scientific results; gender equality; ethics; and dissemination/science education.¹⁰⁷ In Made4You, the monitoring of RRI aspects was performed as part of task 6.4 'RRI Watch'. Throughout the task, RRI aspects were analysed and dealt as follows: public engagement in R&I activities (in WP1 'Engagement and Community Growth'); open access to scientific results as well as and dissemination/science education (in WP5 'dissemination and outreach'); gender equality (in WP7 'Project Management'). This WP (WP6) addressed especially the aspects related to ethics governance, which were by supplemented WP8 deliverables and concerned two

¹⁰² The 'Good Samaritan' doctrine is traditionally known in common law legal systems (Vu-Dinh & Marlan). It consists in shielding from liability for those who give reasonable assistance to others whom they believe to be injured, ill, in peril, or otherwise incapacitated.

¹⁰³ For some comparative research on Good Samaritan laws see for instance, Pardun, J. T. (1998). Good Samaritan Laws: A Global Perspective. *Loyola of Los Angeles International and Comparative Law Review*, 20, 591; The DAN LEGAL NETWORK. The Good Samaritan Law Across Europe. http://www.daneurope.org/c/document_library/get_file?uuid=c09228f3-a745-480b-9549-d9fc8bbbd535&groupId=10103.

¹⁰⁴ European Commission. (n.d.). Responsible research & innovation. <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>.

¹⁰⁵ European Commission. (n.d.). Public Engagement and responsible research and innovation. <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/node/766>.

¹⁰⁶ *ibid.*

¹⁰⁷ Adaptation on *ibid.*, having regard to Grant Agreement, at p. 28. See also *infra*, sections 4.3 and 4.4.

crucial aspects: the involvement of human participants in the research and the processing of personal data (and particular categories thereof, including data concerning health) during the project. The first was treated in D8.1 in D6.1,¹⁰⁸ the latter in D8.1 and D6.1.¹⁰⁹

4.2 RRI and Critical Making

Responsible Research and Innovation is frequently understood as “a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view on the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products” (von Schomberg, 2011, 9). In another publication, von Schomberg (2013) clarified that the deliberation around the value of innovations has to include citizens and civil society. The focus is not on the value of innovations, but on the values embedded in innovations (Felt 2018). RRI is thus not only about the avoidance of unintended consequences (of a specific innovation, etc), but about pro-active forms of anticipatory governance supporting ways of developing these innovations (ibid., Nordmann 2014).

In their definition of RRI, Stilgoe et al. (2013) also focus on the aspect of anticipation. “Responsible innovation means taking care of the future through collective stewardship of science and innovation in the present” (ibid., p. 1570). According to their views, RRI is a form of governance that includes a forward-looking instead of a consequentialist view on responsibility. This involves anticipatory governance, constructive or real-time technology assessment, upstream engagement, etc. They propose four dimensions for RRI: **anticipation, reflexivity, inclusion and responsiveness**.

While experts already predict a paradigm shift in the innovation process caused by the maker movement, we must not forget to critically reflect its responsibility in relation to core RRI aspects, such as **ethics, citizen-empowerment, or openness** and relate them to the four dimensions above. Based on current definitions, the “**critical making**” subcategory of the maker movement seems to be the most similar to RRI. Matt Ratto, an associate professor at the University of Toronto, was the first to coin the term “Critical Making” as an academic term. He used the term to “*theoretically and pragmatically connect two modes of engagement with the world that are often held separate—critical thinking, typically understood as conceptually and linguistically based, and physical “making,” goal-based material work*” (Ratto 2011, p253).

Other sources for a responsible and critical technical practice are Agre (1997) and the Critical Engineering Manifesto, released in 2011¹¹⁰. Agre (1997) calls for an increase awareness and critical reflection on hidden assumptions, ideologies

¹⁰⁸ See, Made4You D8.1. H - Requirement No. 1, and its further illustration D6.1 in section 2.5 (‘Key data protection legal requirements and recommendations for Made4You’).

¹⁰⁹ See D8.2, and D6.1, ibid (section 2.5).

¹¹⁰ <https://criticalengineering.org>

and values underlying technology designs. The Critical Engineering Manifesto by Oliver, Savičić, Vasiliev (2011 – 2017) provides thought-provoking points for engineers and other technology developers to critically reflect on the impacts of technical infrastructures they design and the politics and power relations behind them.

4.3 Responsible Making Principles

Inspired by these critical and reflective approaches to making the Global Innovation Gathering (GIG) assembled a group of global makers to jointly define a set of Responsible Making principles. GIG, one of the core partners in this project, represents a global community of innovation hubs, makerspaces, hackerspaces and other grassroots innovation community spaces and initiatives as well as individual innovators, makers, technologists and changemakers. In December 2019, a diverse cohort of experienced makers from this network coming from Germany, Brazil, India, Iraq, Kenya, Singapore, Sri Lanka, and South Sudan gathered, driven by the inquiry “whether and how makerspaces across the world can become centres for positive social and ecological impact, while integrating models that ensure financial self-sufficiency”. They jointly defined a set of Sustainable Making Principles for Makers (Nuesse and Wanalo, 2020), which strongly relate to RRI principles, with a greater shift towards socially responsible open innovation:

1. **Make** things that make sense: Create products and solutions that solve fundamental, real-world problems.
2. **Integrate** Local Knowledge: Design with the community, leveraging on local knowledge and experience, as well as the local resources & assets available.
3. **Include** Ecosystem Services: Aim to give back more than you take from the environment and include accounting practices that value the natural resources used.
4. **Build** for Continuity: Design for the present and future; build social capacity & aim for financial self-sufficiency.
5. **Share** How You Make: Develop a set of guidelines that provide a framework for openly documenting everything about the making of the project.

These principles were discussed in the Careables team to see how they also apply to the special focus of making open healthcare products. In a collaborative process we adapted these principles to the following **careables responsible making principles**:

1. **Make things that make sense:** Create solutions that answer to real personal problems or needs.
2. **Co-design with others:** Make space for diverse skills, competences, knowledge, and experiences to merge and come to new and meaningful solutions.

3. **Empower people:** Teach others so that everyone can become more technologically literate and see the potentials.
4. **Share How You Make:** Openly document the making of the project enabling its replication and choose the most appropriate licenses for your project.
5. **Be aware of limits:** Consider any gaps of knowledge when you design for health and care, ask the people you design for and clinicians for support and feedback and follow quality and safety standards.

Table 2 Careables responsible making principles

Figure 1 Careables responsible making principles

4.4 Additional RRI practice recommendations

These core principles for responsible making in healthcare reflect most of the areas or key themes subsumed under the term RRI, namely ethics, gender equality, open access, public engagement and science education. While co-designing and producing DIY healthcare products (= responsible making) is the core of this project, complementary activities, such as communication, impact assessment, etc. have to consider RRI principles as well. The recommendations that we suggest in the following are based on the work of the RRI-Tools project¹¹¹.

ETHICS: in order to follow ethical principles in innovation projects integrity, consideration for the ideas and concerns of others, and alignment with social values have to be met. To achieve this, it is important to follow informed consent procedures and ensure data protection and confidentiality. We support the recommendations from RRI-Tools to follow practical ethical guidelines, such as

¹¹¹ <https://rri-tools.eu/>.

the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity¹¹² and KARIM's Introduction to Responsible Innovation Criteria — a practical guide to responsible innovation.¹¹³

GENDER EQUALITY: Gender aspects have been under focus in the maker movement for some years. There is awareness about a gender bias and about the fact that many maker spaces are relatively homogenous in their audience – white, young and male (Holbert 2016, Voigt et al. 2017). In order to engage women and girls in their community, some maker spaces have resorted to offering and advertising “feminine” maker projects such as weaving, sewing, knitting, humanitarian/service projects. Holbert's research shows that “when making is framed as being a set of practices, skills, and technologies to give back to and support members of one's community,” girls' motivation and persistence were both high throughout the making activity; the girls also indicated an interest in future making that would help others (Holbert 2016). Thus, responsible making in healthcare has the potential to counteract the gender imbalance. To balance the gender bias, we suggest developing further measures to support the gender awareness of maker movement and to encourage women and all genders to participate in innovation practices. Gender should not be regarded as a binary concept, but rather fluid. Co-design teams are encouraged to explore opportunities for all genders and strive for gender equality when building their teams.

OPEN ACCESS - OPENNESS: While RRI recommendations tend to focus on open access to research data, methods and results we want to adapt the concept of openness for the purpose of personalized open healthcare initiatives. An often-claimed characteristic of the maker movement is its strong commitment towards openness.¹¹⁴ Makers are keen on realizing openness as much as possible. Openness and sharing seem to be key principles that makers abide by according to Millard et. al (2018). Openness is practiced by the sharing of ideas and designs locally in maker spaces, and by learning online in the wider community using multiple platforms for uploading designs and projects for other makers to use and adapt. However, for makers with commercial ambitions, it is also challenging to reconcile the value of openness and protection, when running a maker business and entering into a capitalist market. Thus, openness challenges the business model of makers, as we have seen also in the case of some *careables*. Although there are some existing business models for open source hardware more is needed than that, e.g. models for the monetisation of expertise or certification of quality of OSHW (Thompson, 2008).

¹¹² Allea. (2017). The European code of conduct for research integrity. <https://allea.org/code-of-conduct/>.

¹¹³ See HIN, G., DAIGNEY, M., HAUDEBAULT, D., RASKIN, K., BOUCHE, Y. and PAVIE, X. (2014). Introduction to Responsible Innovation Criteria. KARIM.

¹¹⁴ Millard, J., Sorivelle, M., Deljanin, S., Unterfrauner, E., & Voigt, C. (2018). Is the Maker Movement Contributing to Sustainability? Sustainability, 10(7), 2212. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10072212>
D6.3 Validation and policy recommendations including Guidelines on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

In its commitment to openness, which relates to the large umbrella of open science and innovation, the maker movement is a strong advocate and driver of standards for open hardware.¹¹⁵ Open innovation, knowledge sharing, and peer-to-peer learning are central to the maker movement's ideology (Capdevila 2013). At the same time, the Open Source Hardware (OSHW) movement is inspiring many to upload blueprints for societally relevant prototypes into open repositories such as the Careables.org platform. While we see some first business models emerging to support Open Source Hardware (Pearce 2017), we strongly encourage to follow the path of openness and the sharing of knowledge, experiences and designs in open repositories.

PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT – TARGET GROUP ENGAGEMENT: In RRI guidelines multi-actor engagement is strongly recommended. For the creation of DIY personalized healthcare solutions, such as *careables*, a diverse set of actors need to be involved. As we have shown in our numerous co-design events (see e.g. Made4You D1.3), the active engagement of specific target groups from the general public is possible and rewarding. We encourage to open the design process for a wide interested public as creative solutions often emerge from the interplay between different expertise, views and opinions. And we would like to stress again that the careables principles are based on the value of making solutions WITH people, not for people.

SCIENCE EDUCATION – MAKER SKILLS EDUCATION: Although not a mandatory element of RRI, training activities and sharing the knowledge with others has been an important aspect for the careables community (see e.g. Made4You D4.3). Makerspaces are often characterised as spaces for collaboration, information sharing, reflection and learning.¹¹⁶ Incidental as well as intentional learning takes place in the co-design and making processes, as they are often linked with creativity, collaborative problem solving, digital competence and entrepreneurship. The knowledge sharing and learning aspect is thus also a core element of the careables responsible making principles (see above) and has likewise been stressed by Ratto (2011) in his analysis of critical making. Next to the training of specific maker and creative design skills, educational activities may also include creating an exhibition with the results and inviting specific target groups, such as schools, or healthcare professionals. We strongly recommend considering educational aspects as part of any co-design activity in responsible making, supporting the principle of empowerment.

¹¹⁵ E.g. Prototype Fund in Germany: <https://prototypefund.de/>.

¹¹⁶ See Vuorikari, R., Ferrari, A., Punie, Y. (2019). Makerspaces for Education and Training – Exploring future implications for Europe. doi:10.2760/946996
D6.3 Validation and policy recommendations including Guidelines on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

5. Conclusions

This deliverable (D6.3) had **three main objectives**: providing **evaluations** on the legal requirements implemented throughout the Made4You project; outlining **recommendations** for policymakers to enable the flourishing of open healthcare solutions in Europe, and distilling **guidelines on RRI**.

As regards the first objective, this document presented its evaluations by following the key legal frameworks already illustrated in D6.1 and D6.2 (section 2): privacy and data protection law, intellectual property rights, tort law and liability, and medical devices law. In light of the evaluations and findings for every subject matter, specific challenges ahead and recommendations were identified. As regards privacy and data protection, after the end of the project, it is recommended to the Careables.org platform owners to review **data protection roles and responsibilities**, and update existing data protection documentation, where needed (section 2.1). For intellectual property, as often noticed (section 2.2), a crucial challenge in practice consists in the lack of awareness for existing intellectual property rights. This risk, usually due to the informal nature of knowledge sharing in Fablabs/maker spaces, could be mitigated in Fablabs and maker spaces by setting-up of ad hoc **policies to promote the respect of IPRs**. Regarding tort law and liability (section 2.3), the general recommendation is adding **warning clauses or disclaimers to the project documentation** and evaluating insurance practices for the use of the healthcare solutions. For medical devices legislation, it is recommended to **assess the scope and application of MDL** to evaluate how to enact the relevant MDL legal requirements (section 2.4).

As regards the second objective the document proposed key policy recommendations to remove barriers and foster the flourishing of open healthcare solutions in the EU (section 3.1), which were elaborated in light of the experience accrued in the project. The first set of recommendations called on the EU legislator for establishing a **consumers' right to repair**. The second set recommendations asked for considering safeguards and approval mechanisms for **medical devices approval in healthcare emergencies**. Recommendations to policymakers were integrated with broader considerations on research areas worth to be researched in future (section 3.2), i.e., the **role of makers** (household and professional activities, or *tertium genus*), the novel possibilities opened by MDR for **healthcare maker spaces**, and the application of **Good Samaritan laws in the makers' context**.

In its third objective, the deliverable elaborated on the notion of RRI (section 4) where it enlisted the **careables responsible making principles** (section 4.3). In practice, it is recommended to apply these principles while at the same time taking **additional RRI aspects into consideration** (section 4.4) which include ethics, gender equality, open access – openness, public engagement – target group engagement, science education – maker skills education.

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D6.3 Validation and policy recommendations including Guidelines on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

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